

ADHESION PERFORMANCE OF UHMWPE AFTER DIFFERENT SURFACE MODIFICATION TECHNIQUES

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SUMMARY: The aim of the study was to investigate adhesion of UHMWPE after different surface treatments.

Three gas-phase surface modification techniques were investigated, namely UV/Ozone, corona discharge and radio frequency glow discharge plasma, as well as abrasion. The surface treated samples were examined using water contact-angle, surface energy and roughness measurements, as well as single lap-joint shear testing using polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) bone cement and methylmethacrylate (MMA) adhesive.

Corona and glow-discharge treatments were found to activate the surface as shown by an increase in surface energy of over 100% in an order of less than a minute, corresponding to an increase in ultimate shear stress from 0.12 to 0.40MPa. In contrast, UV/Ozone required exposure times in the order of minutes to have an effect that was still incomparable to the other gas-phase treatments examined. Abrasion produced slightly better adhesion properties for single lap-joints bonded with PMMA compared to the corona treatment. The best treatment was found to be a combined treatment of surface roughening for 10s and subsequently a 90s glow-discharge treatment, resulting in failure of the UHMWPE sheet material.

KEYWORDS: Joint replacement, Fixation, UHMWPE, Adhesion, Surface modification.

INTRODUCTION

The total joint replacement (TJR) is a common treatment for degenerative joint diseases such as rheumatoid arthritis and osteoarthritis, mainly revealed in cases of excessive pain and radiographic evidence of a destructive joint [1]. A conventional TJR consists of a Cobalt Chromium (CoCr) convex component articulating against an ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE) concave component. Good results, in terms of component fixation and post-operative patient satisfaction are obtained for hip and knee replacements [2], but they are unsatisfactory for shoulder [3], elbow [4] and ankle replacements [5]. Loosening is one of the main post-operative complications and results must be improved.

Two methods of fixation are commonly used, namely cemented and bone ingrowth fixation, generally used for older and younger patients, respectively. In case of cemented fixation, the prepared bone stock is filled with unhardened polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) bone cement, the component is then positioned and held in place until the PMMA has hardened.

Adhered fixation of UHMWPE components is difficult because the UHMWPE molecule is

inert and non-polar in nature. Cemented components will mainly rely on mechanical interlocking, especially in combination with PMMA, which is more a filler than an adhesive. To improve mechanical locking, the UHMWPE cup components have grooves and holes at the backside surface of the component. This requires a large amount of bone removal and weakens the surrounding structure, making revision surgery, when needed, troublesome [6]. Additionally, fretting of the unbonded interface between UHMWPE and PMMA may occur, leading to third body wear particles between the CoCr and UHMWPE articulating surfaces [7].

Improving the adhesion performance of UHMWPE may lead to improved long-term fixation of current components. Additionally, geometrical new designs may be developed, fixated partially or completely by adhesion, leading to easier surgery and less bone removal.

Current viable surface modification techniques for applications in the biomedical field are gas-phase based treatments as reviewed by Chu et al. (2002) [8]. Surface oxidation of polymers using gas-phase surface modification has been frequently investigated, such as corona [9,10,11], radio frequency glow discharge [9,11,12] and UV/Ozone treatments [11,13,14]. Surface oxidation is the primary mechanism of these surface modification techniques and show better wettability and improved adhesion properties than unmodified polymers [9,11].

Up to now, previous studies have fully focused on the chemical aspects of these treatments with in-depth analysis of the surface chemistry. Rather than repeating these analyses, the present study intends to go one step further in applying this knowledge to improve the adhesive properties of these biomedical polymers.

The aim of the study is to investigate the adhesion of single lap-joints made out of medical grade UHMWPE after a UV/Ozone, corona or radio frequency glow discharge treatment. In addition, mechanical abrasion and a combination of methods are also considered for comparison. A number of surface analyses were employed to better understand the changes on the surface.

MATERIALS

Medical grade UHMWPE samples (110x25x1.4mm) (Chirulen 1020, Poly-Hi Solidur GmbH, Vreden, Germany) were cleaned using isopropanol and underwent different surface treatments.

After undergoing one of the treatments, samples were either evaluated by wettability and surface energy or bonded together by PMMA bone cement (Palamed, Ortomed, Dordrecht, Netherlands) or MMA structural adhesive (MA300, ITW Plexus, Kettering, UK). Since PMMA is not an adhesive, MMA was used due to its similar chemical structure to PMMA, to gain better insight as to the extent of the treatment chosen.

Surface treatments

The applied surface modification techniques were UV/Ozone, corona and glow discharge treatments. Detailed workings of these surface treatments and their industrial applications have been described elsewhere [8,11].

A simple fourth surface modification technique, surface roughening, was used to investigate the effect of increased surface area on adhesion. Additionally, a combination of treatments was investigated. The different surface treatment methods are described below in detail.

UV/Ozone treatment

An in-house UV/Ozone apparatus was assembled using an 80Watt mercury vapour Heraeus Noble light (NNIQ120) (Figure 1a). Wavelengths were of the order of 184.9 and 253.7nm and the samples were placed 20mm away from the source. The tests were performed at atmospheric conditions and samples were treated within a time range of 0 and 30min.

UV/Ozone requires long treatment times and penetrates deepest into the bulk material [11,15]. As this might affect mechanical properties, stiffness and strength of control and treated samples were measured, but no differences in mechanical properties were found within the samples tested.

Corona treatment

A TIGRES Corona gun CKG with a TIGRES power supply of 50Hz (Tigres GmbH, Rellingen, Germany) was used in this indirect corona treatment (Figure 1b). The gun consists of two metal electrode bars 15mm apart, between which a homogeneous corona discharge of 50KHz is ignited. Compressed air flows at atmospheric conditions in-between the electrodes, forcing the discharge towards the substrate in the form of a cone with a parabolic base. Pre-tests had shown that the optimum operating distance between the source and the substrate was 10mm. Samples were then treated within a range of 0 to 120s. Manually moving the samples underneath the corona gun ensured that a wide enough surface area was treated, as demonstrated by the small scatter of the evaluation results for different locations on the samples.

Glow Discharge treatment

The glow discharge treatment was performed using a plasma apparatus (TNO laboratories Eindhoven, The Netherlands) (Figure 1c). The glow discharge was generated using a 13.56MHz ENI ACG-3 radiofrequency generator, coupled to an Astech ATH-50 matching impedance network, which minimises the reflected power. A glass reaction chamber with diameter and length of 50 and 165mm, respectively, was used to contain the plasma. The chamber was fitted with an air inlet and surrounded by 10 turns of copper coil with a diameter of 1.8mm. The pressure needed to produce stable uniform plasma at the specified frequency was 1mbar. A rotary pump with an inlet valve was used to pump the entire plasma system and to keep the pressure consistently at this low value.

Cleaned samples were positioned in the glass chamber, which was filled with atmospheric air. The reactor chamber was then evacuated for 1 minute, before initiating the plasma by increasing the input power to the coil and decreasing the glass chamber pressure.

Two variables affected the level of activation of the surface; time of treatment and input power needed to initiate the plasma. The optimum input power of 200W was found through the results of single lap-joint shear strength pre-tests. Fixing this value, the treatment time was varied between 0-120 seconds.

Following treatment, the samples were kept in flowing gas for 5 minutes before the reactor was evacuated. To allow for the decay of free radicals, air was allowed to enter the chamber to raise the pressure to atmospheric level.

Mechanical abrasion

To investigate the effect of surface area on the adhesive properties, samples were treated with 80 P-Grade sandpaper, which was mounted onto a sanding machine (Metabo, Nürtingen, Germany) to ensure that samples had the same abrasion motion. Samples were treated for 2, 5 and 10 seconds.

TEST METHODS

Surface analysis techniques and single lap-joint shear tests were performed to investigate bonding characteristics and shear strength. For all surface analyses and shear strength experiments three samples were used, except for the shear strength experiments after aging in a 0.9% NaCl solution, for which 2 single lap-joints were used.

Surface roughness

The effect of the different surface treatments on the surface roughness R_a of the UHMWPE samples have been measured using a roughness tester (Surtronic 3P, Taylor-Hobson, Leicester, England). The treated and control UHMWPE samples were manually pulled under the needle of the Surtronic 3P, in two perpendicular directions, 3 times for each direction and then averaged. The maximum error was calculated by taking half the difference between the maximum and minimum measured values: $\max \text{ error} = 0.5(x_{\max} - x_{\min})$.

Wettability and surface energy

Wettability, indicating the spreading of a fluid drop over a surface, is a measure for adhesion performance. This can be indicated by the water contact angle, which is taken as the angle between the sample surface inside the drop and the tangent of the drop at the sample surface as shown in Figure 1d. A smaller angle indicates better wettability and adhesion. Wettability was measured using a Ramé-Hart 100 contact goniometer (Ramé-Hart, inc, Mountain Lakes, USA). A $3\mu\text{l}$ drop of water was placed manually onto the surface and the tangential cone method was used to model the shape of the drop and to measure the water contact angle. The water contact angle has been measured at six different locations on each sample to indicate treatment homogeneity.

With the same equipment, measurements of the surface energy and their polar and dispersive contributions were taken using the Owens-Wendt-Rabel-Kaelbe method, described in further detail in [17]:

$\sigma = \sigma^d + \sigma^p$, where σ^d and σ^p are the dispersive and polar parts of the surface energy respectively. Together with Young's equation ($\gamma_{sv} = \gamma_{sl} + \gamma_{lv} \cos \alpha$, where γ_{sv} , γ_{sl} , γ_{lv} are the surface energies between the solid-vapour, solid-liquid and liquid-vapour interfaces), it can be derived that the polar and dispersive part of the surface energy of the substrate can be found using 5 fluids with different polarity and known parameters. It is the polar part of the surface energy that is of particular importance because it is this part that may be changed through surface modification. The polar part indicates a change in the number of oxygen-based functional groups that have been introduced to the surface during treatments and it is these functional groups that the adhesive will chemically bond to. Thus, a higher presence of oxygen-based functional groups results in a higher polar energy. Five liquids of volume $3\mu\text{l}$ and varying surface tensions were used; purified water, glycerine, formaldehyde, aniline and tri-tolyl-phosphate.

Fig. 1: Surface modification techniques and the water contact angle. (a) UV/Ozone treatment, (b) corona treatment, (c) rf glow discharge treatment, (d) definition of the water contact angle

Interfacial shear strength

A common evaluation method of adhesive properties is shear testing of bonded lap joints. Although the applied interfacial shear load is a non-physiological load, shear stresses may occur in cemented prosthetic components, especially in the case of flat backside surfaces [16] and around grooves and holes for mechanical locking.

Two UHMWPE samples (110x25x1,4 mm) with 20 mm overlap were used. Before mixing, a small amount of glass beads of 0.8 and 0.2 mm diameter was added to the PMMA and MMA, respectively, to ensure a homogenous thickness of the adhesive layer. A thicker interface has been chosen for PMMA, as the bone cement layer is normally thicker than engineering adhesive layers.

After bonding and curing for at least 24 hours, the single lap-joints were tested on a 20kN Zwick testing apparatus (Zwick GmbH & Co., Ulm, Germany). Samples were clamped at both ends and tests were performed at environmental conditions at room temperature and cross-head speeds of 3 and 6 mm/min for the samples bonded with relatively stiff PMMA and more flexible MMA, respectively. Test speeds are chosen to minimize both the influence of viscoelasticity and material creep.

RESULTS

Surface roughness

The surface roughness of the UHMWPE samples after the different treatments can be found in Table 2. Except for the abrasion treatment, no significant difference of the surface roughness was found between the treated and untreated samples.

Water contact angle

A summary of measured contact angles is graphically represented in Figure 2. The measurements were also taken after a waiting period of ten minutes, as this was the maximum time that the samples were left before bonding and no change was found. Also, very small scatter was found for the six different measurement locations on the samples.

A dramatic decrease in contact angles was seen after a couple of seconds for both the corona and glow-discharge treatments, minutes for the UV/Ozone and not at all after the abrasion treatment. This indicates that UHMWPE hydrophobicity can be decreased markedly. Complete wetting resulted from the glow discharge at 25s, which was not matched by any other treatment.

Predictably, increasing the surface roughness increases the contact angle, which is the result of local peaks and valleys on the surface. Additionally, increasing the surface area of an already inert and hydrophobic substrate only provides more area that the water cannot spread over and hence the measured contact angle is larger.

Surface Energy

The variation of surface energy with treatment time is presented in Figure 3. The increase in surface energy by the surface treatments is strongly related to the increase in the polar part of the surface energy.

It appears that the glow discharge is the most efficient treatment of the UHMWPE substrates, achieving in less than 20s, a polar and overall surface energy that is reached after 60s of corona, and not at all by the UV/Ozone treatment. The surface energy has seemingly reached a maximum at 20s and stays at this value for all times tested afterwards. This might indicate that the maximum surface energy of UHMWPE has been reached, or that there was not enough reactive oxygen species present in the vacuum to be implanted into the surface.

Both the corona and glow-discharge treatments produce a polar part of the surface energy that becomes stronger than the dispersive part with time, whilst the same trend is not observed with the UV/Ozone method. The effect of this treatment on UHMWPE has to be questioned

Fig. 2: Variation of the contact angle with treatment time ($t=0$ is control sample)

since the polar force gives an indication as to the extent of oxidation of the surface. It is apparent, with a maximum change of just over 10mN/m compared to 35mN/m for the plasma treatments, that UV/Ozone has very little effect on UHMWPE from this evidence alone. In all cases there is a peak in the surface energies and it would be judicious to assume that the optimum treatment would be found in this time region, for afterwards, not only is there a fall in the polar component, but the efficiency of the treatment is also decreased.

Interfacial shear strength

Results of the interfacial shear strength experiments for UHMWPE samples bonded by PMMA and MMA are given in Table 3 and in Figure 4.

Although all treatments have improved the ultimate shear strength of the UHMWPE/PMMA system, the extent of the improvement differed for individual treatments. Single lap-joints of treated UHMWPE samples bonded by PMMA and MMA behaved similarly, both showing the same trends. The physical interaction that could be induced at the PMMA/UHMWPE interface was increased to the point where the PMMA was able to behave as an adhesive. Both abrasion and glow discharge had a greater effect for lap-joints bonded by PMMA than the UV/Ozone and corona treatments and, when used in combination, it was able to approach the shear strength of MMA-bonded samples. The extent of the increase in interfacial strength of the UHMWPE/MMA system was such that the failure mode had changed from cohesive failure to failure within the substrate with the onset of necking and plastic deformation of the UHMWPE samples, displaying the potential of this treatment.

The general trends for UV/Ozone and corona are similar to those as found by that of the surface energy, with the maximum shear stress values found at points of maximum surface energy. This tendency is not followed with the glow discharge, which displays an increasing trend of shear strength increase to beyond the treatment time as expected by the wettability results.

DISCUSSION

Plasma and UV/Ozone treatments have improved the adhesion properties of UHMWPE to different extents. Immediately it is clear that with respect to efficiency, UV/Ozone is the poorest performer in all the methods used to examine the techniques and exposure time necessary is of the order of minutes compared to seconds for the others. The case may be that UHMWPE is transparent to the effects of this treatment and a similar result was found by Strobel et al. (1996) [11]. Numerous studies have stated that bulk damage and ageing transpires from UV/Ozone treatment [18,19] with no such observation from the other treatments and this is a serious factor when considering its use with biomaterials.

Fig. 3: Variation of surface energy with treatment time ($t=0$ is control sample)

Adsorption of atmospheric surface contaminants and reorganisation of the surface molecules are two processes that occur [20,21] and hydrophobic recovery is an unavoidable consequence of treated samples. Øiseth et al. (2002) had shown that glow discharge treatments took orders of days for treated high-density-polyethylene to reach such a recovery, and 24 hours for significant change [22]. Friedrich et al. (1998) found similar results with indirect corona treatment on polypropylene films [18]. From water contact angle measurements performed in this study, such ageing was not apparent in the short times tested. The time taken between treatment and application of the adhesive was kept as short as possible but with these results, such precautions were not necessary and this is particularly beneficial in the case of surgery where extra time pressure due to treating the prosthesis can be avoided.

There is a strong correlation between the variation of surface energy with time of treatment and the shear stress results for UV/Ozone and corona discharge. The increase of surface energy is due to an increase in polar energy. Since an increase in the polar energy is related to an increase in the presence of oxygen-based functional groups at the substrate surface, this results in a greater number of chemical bonds that can be made with the PMMA or MMA. This work therefore supports studies as performed by Owens (1975), who experimented with corona treatment upon low-density polyethylene [23]. There is a direct relation between the surface energy measured on the plastics and the shear stress measured on the adhesively bonded samples. The mechanisms leading to an increase in the adhesive properties are based on the increase of polar groups on the surface. However, the kind of groups generated on the surface may be slightly different and the different mechanical etching effect of each surface activation method differs as well leading to a time dependence of surface properties [23]. This results in different adhesive properties of the plastics after bonding.

The interesting discovery in this study on UHMWPE surface modification is that surface energy, and particularly the polar force measurements, can be a very good qualitative predictor of the adhesive behaviour of UHMWPE. Hence, future work focused on improving the described surface treatments can be done using surface energy trends only. Although these similar trends with the water contact angle and shear stress results were found, wettability data can provide an over-optimistic prediction as to how the adhesion properties will improve. For example, glow discharge treated samples can have contact angle close to 0° , which is not reflected in the shear strength using either PMMA or MMA.

The extent as to how far these results should be taken into consideration with respect to the adhesive properties however, is debatable. Surface oxidation methods do result in varying amounts of chain scission of the polymer structure, lowering the molecular weight of the outermost surfaces [11,20]. The lower molecular weight material is water-soluble thereby clouding the interpretation of the treated samples giving false information as to the extent of

Fig. 4: Variation of interfacial shear stress with treatment time ($t=0$ is control sample)

wetting of the underlying surface, which is insoluble. In addition, there is also variation in measurements due to a number of contributing reasons. The substrate surface may not be perfectly smooth due to machining lines and therefore the contact angles can show differences with position. On sheet material, the liquid drops tended to elongate depending on the direction of the production process, resulting in the same effect of varying contact angles with position. Nevertheless, this effect is assumed to be small and as a comparison, both the water contact angle and surface energy measurements are very useful tools.

Although all treatments have improved the ultimate shear strength of the UHMWPE/PMMA system, the extent of the improvement was not the same. A similar trend had occurred with the MMA adhesive with shear stress values that were generally twice as high, except for abrasion. However, to see if the effect of the best surface treatment as investigated could be further improved, a combination treatment of abrasion followed by glow discharge was examined. Recalling that PMMA has little to no adhesive properties, the combination treatment resulted in lap shear strength that completely outperformed all other UHMWPE/PMMA single lap-joints. In fact, for results comparable and better than that of other treatments, the combination treatment needed less glow discharge exposure. This combined treatment is not only more efficient, that is, less glow discharge treatment time needed for optimum shear strength results, but shear strength values were able to approach that of the MMA bonded samples. The same trend was found by Ogawa et al. (1999), in their study on interfacial shear strength of UHMWPE Fibre/PE systems. Their results also indicate that there is an equal contribution to interfacial shear strength from surface roughness and surface modification [10].

It has been found that a combination of treatments was the best way to improve the adhesive properties of the UHMWPE/PMMA system in a simple shear load case. It has also been found that the effect of the combined treatment is more than simply summing the effect of the separate treatments, as abrasion increases the effective area for following surface treatments. Future studies are necessary to investigate the behaviour of these samples under dynamic (fatigue) loading. However, the results obtained in this study have shown that improved fixation can be acquired through surface modifications techniques. The potential to change current prosthetic designs in TJR that are based on fixation by adhesion might be realised. Additionally, research into a structural adhesive for in-vivo use may be very worthwhile.

CONCLUSIONS

The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of different surface modification techniques on the adhesion performance of UHMWPE, when bonded with PMMA and MMA.

Adhesion properties improved to various degrees after all treatments in the following order of effectiveness of the treatments: UV/Ozone, corona, abrasion, glow discharge and a combined abrasion and glow discharge treatment and was not affected by aging in a 0.9% NaCl at 37° C. Adhesive performance of UHMWPE with PMMA showed similar trends as in combination with MMA, which performed superiorly. Future research both into a new adhesive for in-vivo use and component design would be tremendously worthwhile, especially for this new concept of glenoid fixation.

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